

Global Dominance: Leading the Copra Production Industry Worldwide

By: Worldatlas

The exceptional resilience of copra (coconut) raw materials allows for cultivation in various soil types, albeit with a preference for relatively high rainfall. Coconut's natural habitat is found in coastal areas and on the fringes of deserts. Primarily grown and harvested by small-scale farmers, coconut production is concentrated in island and coastal regions such as Fiji and Samoa, as well as in humid tropical areas like India, the Philippines, Thailand, and Indonesia.

Coconut, a valuable tropical plant species, serves as a versatile resource with a wide array of products derived from it. These coconut products range from clothing and animal feed to beauty creams. The kernel is harvested for its edible flesh and delicious water, while the husk is utilized for its strong fibers. However, the most crucial aspect is the extraction, processing, and marketing of coconut oil for culinary, medicinal, and cosmetic purposes. Typically, the flesh is first dried to 6% moisture content to create copra, which is then transported to factories

worldwide where it is processed into oil. Less common but more valuable is virgin coconut oil, directly extracted from raw coconuts.

1. Indonesia - 17.13 Million Metric Tons

Indonesia leads the world in copra production, with the majority being cultivated in the North Sulawesi province. A significant portion of Indonesia's copra is exported internationally, making the country a major player in the global market. Additionally, Indonesia ranks among the largest pineapple producers globally.

2. Philippines - 14.77 Million Metric Tons

The Philippines holds the position of the second-largest copra producer globally. While it previously held the top spot before being surpassed by Indonesia, key production areas in the country include Luzon, South Mindanao, and East Visayas. Approximately a quarter of the total agricultural land dedicated to coconut farming in the Philippines is utilized for copra production.

3. India - 14.68 Million Metric Tons

India stands as the third-largest copra producer worldwide, responsible for over 119 million tons in 2016. Copra production plays a crucial role in India's agricultural industry and overall economy, particularly in rural areas.

4. Sri Lanka - 2.47 Million Metric Tons

As the fourth-largest copra producer globally, the island nation of Sri Lanka closely follows Brazil with an annual production of 2.513 million tons. The warm and sunny climate in Sri

Lanka provides an ideal environment for coconut cultivation, serving as the primary raw material for copra.

5. Brazil - 2.33 Million Metric Tons

Brazil ranks as the fifth-largest copra producer globally, with a production exceeding 2 million tons in 2016. Although not as prominent as Asian countries on this list, Brazil's copra production has been on the rise due to increased demand for coconut-related products. Similar to other nations in this ranking, copra production is a significant contributor to Brazil's economy.

The Future of Copra

The future of copra, the dried kernel of coconuts from which coconut oil is extracted, holds promising prospects as the global demand for sustainable and natural products continues to rise. With an increasing awareness of the environmental impact of traditional agriculture, there is a growing emphasis on organic and eco-friendly farming practices. Copra production stands to benefit from this shift, as coconut trees are inherently resilient and can thrive in diverse ecosystems. Moreover, the versatility of coconut-derived products, ranging from oil to cosmetics and health supplements, positions copra as a valuable commodity in various industries. The ongoing research and development efforts to enhance cultivation techniques and yield efficiency

further contribute to the positive outlook for the future of copra, suggesting that it will play a significant role in the sustainable and lucrative agribusiness landscape.

10 Countries With The Highest Copra Production

Rank	Country	Production in million metric tons
1	Indonesia	17.13
2	Philippines	14.77
3	India	14.68
4	Sri Lanka	2.47
5	Brazil	2.33
6	Vietnam	1.68
7	Mexico	1.29
8	Papua New Guinea	1.19
9	Thailand	0.81
10	Malaysia	0.54